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Numerical solution of fractional delay-integro-differential equations with a weakly singular kernel

Haniye Dehestani*, Yadollah Ordokhani

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematical sciences, Alzahra university, Tehran, Iran

Abstract

In this paper, a new numerical method for solving fractional delay-integro-differential equations (FDIDEs) with a weakly singular kernel is presented. The transformation matrix of Bessel polynomials to Taylor polynomials and Taylor operational matrix of integration are used to transform the equation to a system of algebraic equations. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate the validity and applicability of the technique.

Keywords: Bessel polynomials, Weakly singular delay-integro-differential equations, Operational matrix of integration

Mathematics Subject Classification [2010]: 65D30, 65L70

1 Introduction

In recent years, many phenomena in various branches of science like physics, chemistry and engineering can be modeled more efficiently by the fractional calculus. FDIDEs with a weakly singular kernel have many applications in various areas. These equations appear in the radiative equilibrium, heat conduction problem, elasticity and fracture mechanics [1,2] and so on. Consider the FDIDEs with a weakly singular kernel:

$$\begin{aligned} D^\alpha u(t) &= f\left(t, u(q_0 t), u'(q_1 t), \int_0^{h(t)} \frac{[u(\eta)]^p}{(t-\eta)^\beta} d\eta, \int_0^1 k(t, \eta)[u(\eta)]^p d\eta\right), \\ u(0) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Here, $0 < \alpha, \beta \leq 1$, $0 < q_0, q_1 \leq 1$, D^α denotes the fractional derivative defined by Caputo [3], $f(t)$ and $k(t, \eta)$ are the known functions and $u(t)$ is an unknown function.

*Speaker: h.dehestani@alzahra.ac.ir

2 Bessel polynomials and operational matrices of integration

The n -th degree truncated Bessel polynomials of first kind are defined by [4]

$$J_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!(k+n)!} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right)^{2k+n}, \quad 0 \leq t < \infty, \quad n \in N, \quad (2)$$

where N is chosen the positive integer so that $N \geq n$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. We can transform the Bessel polynomials of first kind to in N -th degree Taylor basis functions. In matrix form as

$$J(t) = DT(t), \quad (3)$$

where D is defined in [4], $J(t) = [J_0(t), J_1(t), \dots, J_N(t)]^T$, and $T(t) = [T_0(t), T_1(t), \dots, T_N(t)]^T$. We can write $k(t, \eta)$ to matrix form as [4]

$$k(t, \eta) \simeq T^T(t)k_t T(\eta), \quad k(t, \eta) \simeq J^T(t)k_b J(\eta). \quad (4)$$

By using Eqs. (3) and (4), we obtain:

$$k_b = (D^T)^{-1}k_t(D)^{-1}, \quad k_t = [{}_t k_{mn}], \quad {}_t k_{mn} = \frac{1}{m!n!} \frac{\partial^{m+n} k(0, 0)}{\partial^m t \partial^n \eta} \quad m, n = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

Now, we obtain operational matrix of integer and fractional order integration of Bessel polynomials as

$$\int_0^t J(\eta) d\eta = tDLT(t), \quad (5)$$

where $L = \text{diag}(1, \frac{1}{2}, \dots, \frac{1}{N+1})$, is called operational matrix of integer order integration of Bessel polynomials. Also, by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integral and there properties, we have

$$I^\alpha J(\eta) = t^\alpha D\xi^\alpha T(t), \quad (6)$$

where $\xi^\alpha = \text{diag}(\frac{\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(2-\gamma)}, \dots, \frac{\Gamma(N+1)}{\Gamma(N+2-\gamma)})$, is called operational matrix of fractional order integration of Bessel polynomials.

3 Method of solution

For solving this problem, we approximate $u'(t)$ by using Bessel polynomials as follows

$$u'(t) \simeq A^T J(t) = A^T DT(t), \quad (7)$$

then,

$$u'(qt) \simeq A^T J(qt) = A^T DT(qt). \quad (8)$$

According to Eqs. (7), (8) and the operational matrix of integration, we get

$$u(t) \simeq tA^T DLT(t), \quad u(qt) \simeq tA^T DLT(qt). \quad (9)$$

Using Eqs. (6) and (7), to obtain the fractional derivative of $u(t)$ as

$$D^\alpha u(t) = I^{1-\alpha} u'(t) \simeq t^{1-\alpha} A^T D\xi^{1-\alpha} T(t). \quad (10)$$

Now, for solving these equations we need to define

$$[u(t)]^p \simeq B^T J(t) = B^T DT(t). \quad (11)$$

Also, we approximate the integral part of Eq. (1) by using Eqs. (4) and (11) as follows

$$\int_0^1 k(t, \eta)[u(\eta)]^p d\eta \simeq \int_0^1 T^T(t) D^T k_b DT(\eta) T^T(\eta) D^T B d\eta = T^T(t) D^T k_b D H D^T B, \quad (12)$$

and

$$\int_0^{h(t)} \frac{[u(\eta)]^p}{(t-\eta)^\beta} d\eta \simeq B^T D \int_0^{h(t)} \frac{T(\eta)}{(t-\eta)^\beta} d\eta = h(t)^\beta B^T D \tilde{S} T(h(t)), \quad (13)$$

where $\tilde{S} = \text{diag}\left(\frac{\Gamma(1-\beta)\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(2-\beta)}, \frac{\Gamma(1-\beta)\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(3-\beta)}, \dots, \frac{\Gamma(1-\beta)\Gamma(1+N)}{\Gamma(2-\beta+N)}\right)$, and H is dual operational matrix of Taylor polynomials, which is defined in [4]. Now, we write fundamental matrix equation corresponding to Eq. (1) as follows

$$\begin{cases} t^{1-\alpha} A^T D \xi^{1-\alpha} T(t) \simeq f\left(t, t A^T D L T(q_0 t), A^T D T(q_1 t), h(t)^\beta B^T D \tilde{S} T(h(t)), T^T(t) D^T k_b D H D^T B\right), \\ [t A^T D L T(t)]^p \simeq B^T D T(t). \end{cases}$$

Then, we collocate this system at the following points $t_i = \frac{2i-1}{2(N+1)}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N+1$. Consequently, we obtain the solution of Eq. (1) under conditions for the unknown vector A by using Newton's iterative method.

4 Error analysis

In this section, we investigate the convergence analysis of our proposed method. We assume that $f(t)$ is a sufficiently smooth function on $[0, 1]$ and $p_N(x)$ is the interpolating polynomial to f at points t_i , where t_i , $i = 0, 1, \dots, N$ are the roots of the $(N+1)$ -degree shifted Chebyshev polynomial in $[0, 1]$, then we have [4]

$$|f(t) - p_N(t)| \leq \frac{M_N}{2^{2N+1}(N+1)!}, \quad M_N \geq \sup_{t \in [0,1]} |f^{(N+1)}(t)|.$$

Theorem 1. Suppose $u(t) \in C^{N+1}[0, 1]$ and $u_N(t) = A^T J(t)$ be the approximate solution obtained by the present method in previous section. If $\tilde{u}_N(t) = \tilde{A}^T \tilde{J}(t)$ be the Bessel polynomials of first kind expansion of the exact solution $u(t)$, where $\tilde{A} = [\tilde{a}_0, \tilde{a}_1, \dots, \tilde{a}_N]^T$, $\tilde{J}(t) = [\tilde{J}_0(t), \tilde{J}_1(t), \dots, \tilde{J}_N(t)]^T$ and $\tilde{J}_n(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!(k+n)!} \left(\frac{t}{2}\right)^{2k+n}$, $0 \leq t < \infty$. The set of Bessel polynomials of first kind $\tilde{J}_n(t)$ in $L^2[0, 1]$ is orthogonal with respect to the weight function $w(t) = t$,

$$\int_0^1 w(t) [\tilde{J}_n(t)]^2 dt = \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(1)]^2.$$

Then obtain the upper bound of the error, as

$$\|f(t) - u_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} \leq \frac{M_N}{2^{2N+\frac{3}{2}}(N+1)!} + \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \theta_N + \|A\|_2 \omega_N, \quad (14)$$

where $\theta_N = \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(1)]^2\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$ and $\omega_N = \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k!(k+n)! 2^{2k+n})^2 (4k+2n+2)}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Proof: we can write

$$\|f(t) - u_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} \leq \|f(t) - \tilde{u}_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} + \|\tilde{u}_N(t) - u_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]}, \quad (15)$$

Since $\tilde{u}_N(t)$ is the best approximation of $u(t)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|f(t) - \tilde{u}_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} &= \left(\int_0^1 |f(t) - \tilde{A}^T \tilde{J}(t)|^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \left(\int_0^1 |f(t) - p_N(t)|^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \left(\frac{M_N^2}{(2^{2N+1}(N+1)!)^2} \int_0^1 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{M_N}{2^{2N+\frac{3}{2}}(N+1)!}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{u}_N(t) - u_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} &= \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N \tilde{a}_n \tilde{J}_n(t) - \sum_{n=0}^N a_n J_n(t) \right\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N (\tilde{a}_n - a_n) \tilde{J}_n(t) \right\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} + \left\| \sum_{n=0}^N a_n (\tilde{J}_n(t) - J_n(t)) \right\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} \\ &= \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N (\tilde{a}_n - a_n) \tilde{J}_n(t) \right]^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N a_n (\tilde{J}_n(t) - J_n(t)) \right]^2 t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{a}_n - a_n|^2 \right] \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{J}_n(t)|^2 \right] t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\int_0^1 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |a_n|^2 \right] \left[\sum_{n=0}^N |\tilde{J}_n(t) - J_n(t)|^2 \right] t dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 t |\tilde{J}_n(t)|^2 dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 |\tilde{J}_n(t) - J_n(t)|^2 t dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$\|\cdot\|_2$ is 2-norm of vectors. Therefore, by use of orthogonality property of Bessel polynomials, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{u}_N(t) - u_N(t)\|_{L_w^2[0,1]} &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(1)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \int_0^1 \left(\sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k t^{2k+n}}{k!(k+n)!2^{2k+n}} \right)^2 t dt \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq \|\tilde{A} - A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{J}_{n+1}(1)]^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \|A\|_2 \left[\sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{k=\lfloor \frac{N-n}{2} \rfloor}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k!(k+n)!2^{2k+n})^2 (4k+2n+2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

According to Eq. (15)-(18), we determine the upper bound of error.

Recent theorem demonstrates that by increasing the number of Bessel polynomials the approximate solutions convergence to exact solution.

5 Numerical results

In this section, three examples are given to demonstrate the applicability and accuracy of our methods.

Table 1: Absolute error with different values of N with $\gamma = 1$ for Example 1.

t_i	Present Method			Ref [3]	variational iteration [6]	Runge-Kutta
	$N = 3$	$N = 6$	$N = 8$	$k = 2, M = 6$	method	method
0.1	2.22×10^{-4}	5.46×10^{-8}	2.30×10^{-10}	4.98×10^{-8}	1.30×10^{-3}	8.68×10^{-4}
0.3	1.24×10^{-4}	4.59×10^{-8}	1.10×10^{-8}	7.78×10^{-9}	2.63×10^{-3}	1.90×10^{-3}
0.5	5.65×10^{-5}	1.59×10^{-7}	5.56×10^{-8}	6.34×10^{-5}	2.83×10^{-3}	2.28×10^{-3}
0.7	4.54×10^{-5}	4.66×10^{-7}	1.47×10^{-7}	4.36×10^{-5}	2.39×10^{-3}	2.27×10^{-3}
0.9	8.34×10^{-6}	1.06×10^{-6}	2.84×10^{-7}	2.80×10^{-5}	1.64×10^{-3}	2.03×10^{-3}

Table 2: The comparison of absolute errors for $N = 2$ and $h(t) = t$ with methods in [1] of Example 2.

t	Present method		CASW	HaarW	ADM	SCW
	$h(t) = \cos(t^2)$	$h(t) = t$	$M = 1, k = 3$	$M = 1, m = 24$	$n = 4$	$M = 3, k = 4$
0	0	0	6.34×10^{-3}	5.82×10^{-3}	4.23×10^{-3}	1.43×10^{-4}
1/6	8.95×10^{-18}	1.39×10^{-16}	1.14×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-2}	9.18×10^{-3}	2.26×10^{-4}
2/6	1.77×10^{-17}	2.76×10^{-16}	9.69×10^{-3}	9.70×10^{-3}	2.43×10^{-2}	5.98×10^{-4}
3/6	2.63×10^{-17}	4.09×10^{-16}	2.95×10^{-3}	3.11×10^{-3}	4.52×10^{-2}	1.12×10^{-3}
4/6	3.45×10^{-17}	5.37×10^{-16}	9.67×10^{-3}	9.70×10^{-3}	8.02×10^{-2}	1.49×10^{-3}
5/6	4.22×10^{-17}	6.56×10^{-16}	2.94×10^{-2}	2.95×10^{-2}	1.04×10^{-1}	2.20×10^{-3}

Example 1. Consider the fractional pantograph differential equation [3, 6]

$$D^\gamma u(t) = -u(t) + 0.1u\left(\frac{4}{5}t\right) + 0.5u'\left(\frac{4}{5}t\right) + (0.32t - 0.5)\exp(-0.8t) + \exp(-t), \quad 0 < \gamma \leq 1,$$

subject to the initial condition $u(0) = 0$. In the case $\gamma = 1$, the exact solution is $u(t) = t \exp(-t)$. In Table 1, we compare the absolute errors of the proposed method for $\gamma = 1$ with method in [3], variational iteration method and Runge-Kutta method.

Example 2. Consider the following fractional order integro-differential equation with weakly singular kernel [1]

$$D^{0.25}u(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{h(t)} \frac{u(\eta)}{(t-\eta)^{\frac{1}{2}}} d\eta + \frac{1}{3} \int_0^1 (t-\eta)u(\eta) d\eta + f(t),$$

and $f(t) = \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(2.75)}t^{1.75} + \frac{\Gamma(4)}{\Gamma(3.75)}t^{2.75} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}h(t)^{\frac{5}{2}}\Gamma(3)}{2\Gamma(\frac{7}{2})} - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}h(t)^{\frac{7}{2}}\Gamma(4)}{2\Gamma(\frac{9}{2})}$, with the condition $u(0) = 0$.

The exact solution is known and it is given by $u(t) = t^2 + t^3$. In Table 2, obtained absolute error between the approximate solutions and the exact solution for various functions of $h(t)$ with $N = 2$. This example considered in other papers, results show that present method more accurate than these methods.

Example 3. Consider the nonlinear equation [5]

$$D^\alpha u(t) = \int_0^t \frac{[u(\eta)]^2}{(t-\eta)^{\frac{1}{2}}} d\eta + \int_0^1 t\eta[u(\eta)]^2 d\eta + f(t),$$

with $f(t) = 3t^2 - \frac{\sqrt{\pi}h(t)^{\frac{13}{2}}\Gamma(7)}{\Gamma(\frac{15}{2})} - \frac{t}{8}$, subject to the initial condition $u(0) = 0$. In the case $\alpha = 1$, the exact solution is $u(t) = t^2$. Numerical results for values of $\alpha = 1, 0.95, 0.85, 0.75$, and the exact solution with $N = 6$ are shown in Figure 1(a). Also, absolute error for $\alpha = 1$ with $N = 6$ is demonstrate in Figure 1(b). From Figure 1(a), we see that, as α approaches 1, the numerical solutions converge to the exact solution.

Figure 1: a) The comparison of $u(t)$ for various values of α with $N = 6$ and the exact solution, b) the absolute error for $\alpha = 1$ with $N = 6$ of Example 3.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we introduce operational matrices of integration and use these matrices to solve fractional delay-integro-differential equations with a weakly singular kernel. Our numerical findings are compared with exact solutions and with the solutions obtained by some other numerical methods. The results of numerical examples demonstrate that this method is more accurate than some existing methods.

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